

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
WIRELESS CHARGING IN MOBILE PHONE
PROJECT REPORT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

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ABSTRACT

Mobile Phones are part of our life. It is the fastest and the easiest medium of communication. Battery life of mobile phone is always been a problem for manufacturers. People are complaining about their mobile's battery life, that they don't have long battery life and they have to charge their phone several times. In this paper a new idea is shown to charge your mobile phone anywhere you want without connecting its charger. This is done using microwaves. Microwaves are the radio waves which provide communication between two mobile phones. The microwave is sent with the message by the transmitter using antenna at the frequency of 2.45GHz. Here we are using Microwaves as the source of energy to charge the phone. We have to add a sensor, a rectenna circuit and a filter in our mobile phone to do the job. By adding these things we can charge our phone using microwave when we talk. So, as we talk more we can charge more!!

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INTRODUCTION

Portable electronic devices are very popular nowadays. As the usage of these portable electronic devices is increasing, the demands for longer battery life are also increasing. These batteries need to be recharged or replaced periodically. It is a hassle to charge or change the battery after a while, especially when there is no power outlet around. Therefore, our team is inspired to design a wireless battery charger. This wireless battery charger is expected to eliminate all the hassles with today's battery technology.

As for now, there are no known companies that are developing the wireless battery charger. This means that there might be a good opportunity in the market for this type of product. Moreover, people tend to spend more money for convenience that meets the price. The outlook of this device is supported by the above predictions.

It would be convenient not having to worry about charging or changing the batteries and still have a working device. The advantage of this device is that it can wirelessly charge up the batteries which can save time and money in a long run for the general public. Base on this concept, the design team has come up with a new way to charge the batteries wirelessly. The project is to make a prototype device that converts microwave signals to DC power. Once the prototype has been proved to be working, it is possible to implement this prototype into other applications such as in television remote control, fire alarm, clock, and places that are far to reach to change battery.

1.1 Electromagnetic Spectrum

As we know that when light shone through the prism it is divided in all the colors which we called rainbow, and technically it is called visible spectrum. So light is made of photons. Photons are bundle of energy. Light is traveling at the speed of 3,00,000 km/hr So when light hit an object coming on its way it actually rebound from its surface. And it comes in to our eyes and we can see the object. But color of the object is seen by us is depend how much amount of energy is rebound as photons from the object. But some theory can't be explained by taking the light as the bunch of photos. So some physicians assume that it is some kind of wave. They define an electromagnetic sanctum of different wave lengths which is divided in two parts. One is electric field and the other is magnetic field.

1.2 Microwave Region

Microwaves are the Radio wave which has the wave length range of 1 cm to 1 meter. And the frequency is 300MHz to 300GHz.Each and every object on the earth absorb different amount of microwave energy. Microwave oven converts this microwave energy in to the frequency which the food absorbs and gets energy from it and get worm. But the bowl containing the food do not get worm because its capacity of absorbing microwave frequency is different! Microwaves are good at carrying information from one place to other. As the microwave penetrates the solid material and also it do not have and effect of weather and rain etc. So it is useful to carry information. There are different frequency bands according to the range of frequencies shown:

Designation	Frequency	Range
L Band	1 to 2	GHz
S Band	2 to 4	GHz
C Band	4 to 8	GHz
X Band	8 to 12	GHz
Ku Band	12 to 18	GHz
K Band	18 to 26	GHz
Ka Band	26 to 40	GHz
Q Band	30 to 50	GHz
U Band	40 to 60	GHz
V Band	46 to 56	GHz
W Band	56 to 100	GHz

We will use S Band for our experiment. As Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) some bands are reserve for some specific purpose. So we can't use it. Here S band is freely available band which we can use for experiment.

WIRELESS POWER TRANSMISSION

Nikolas Tesla is the father of wireless electricity transmission. Who first transmitted electricity without wire. Magnetic induction is the main principle behind the wireless power transmission. As we put one coil carrying current through it, it creates a magnetic field near to it. And if we put other coil over there than it is induce by the first coil and it carry current from it! This is the simple principle behind it.

2.1 Wireless Power Transmission System

William C. Brown demonstrated how power can be transfer through space using microwaves. The concept of wireless power transmission is shown the block diagram.

Figure1

Here as we can see there are two part. One is transmitting part and the other is the Receiving part. At the transmitting end there is one microwave power source which is actually producing microwaves. Which is attach to the Coax-Waveguide and here Tuner is the one which match the impedance of the transmitting antenna and the microwave source. Directional Coupler helps the signal to propagate in a particular direction. It spread the Microwaves in a space and sent it to the receiver side. Receiver side Impedance matching circuit receives the microwave signal through Recteena circuit. This circuit is nothing but the combination of filter circuit and the schottky Diode. Which actually convert our microwave in to the DC power.

2.2 Components of wireless power transmission system

The important components of this system are Microwave generator, Transmitting antenna, and the receiving antenna.

2.2.1. Microwave Generator

The Microwave Generator is the one which generates the microwave of preferred frequency. It generates the Microwave by the interaction of stream of electrons and the magnetic field.

2.2.2 Transmitting Antenna

There are many kind of slotted wave guide antenna available. Like parabolic dish antenna, microstrip patch antenna are the popular type of transmitting antenna.

2.2.3 Rectenna

A **rectenna** is a **rectifying antenna**, a special type of antenna that is used to convert microwave energy into direct current electricity. A simple rectenna element consists of a dipole antenna with an RF diode connected across the dipole elements. The current induced by the microwaves in the antenna is rectified by the diode. Which powers a load connected across the diode. Schottky diodes are used because they have low voltage drop and high speed so that they have low power loss.

Figure 2

SPECIFICATIONS

The design is separated into three subsystems: the transmitter, the antenna, and the charging circuit. This charger will charge the battery by utilizing the microwave signal at 900 MHz frequency. It will convert the microwave signal to DC signal, and then it will use the DC signal to charge the battery. Below are the design specifications of the charger circuit.

Design Specifications	
Source frequencies:	900 MHz
Charging distance:	1 feet
Voltage output:	2.0V
Power output:	60 mW
Battery type:	One AAA

DESIGN OVERVIEW

This wireless battery charger is designed to operate at 900 MHz. In this project, a power transmitter acts as the power source. It will transmit power to the receiver side. And then, the rectifier circuit in the receiver will convert the RF/ microwave signal into DC signal. After the DC signal is produced, the charging circuit will store the power into the battery. Here is the block diagram of the overall design.

Figure: 3

3.1. Transmitter

A magnetron is a diode vacuum tube. Filament in the tube act as the cathode. Magnetron is actually act as a oscillator to produce microwaves. It can be done by putting magnet between the resonating chambers which is the center of the oscillator. These resonating chambers are called the anode of the magnetron. When electrons come out from the cathode it direct towards the Anode. As it pass through the magnetic field it start circulating in the resonating cavity and start producing waves according to its frequency. And the generated RF signal flow outside of the chamber.

Figure: 4 (a)

Figure: 4 (b) - 900 MHz Video/Audio Transmitter

Since the group does not design the transmitter, therefore the design is mainly focus on the receiver side. A power transmitter is bought from a commercial website. It is a 900 MHz video/audio transmitter. Here's the specification of the transmitter.

Power: 12V DC, 900 mA
Output Power: 3 Watts
Operating Frequency: 900 MHz
Connector Type: SMA – Female
Output Impedance: 50 Ω

3.2. Antenna

The antenna plays a very important role. To charge a battery, a high DC power signal is needed. The wireless battery charger circuit must keep the power loss to the minimal. Therefore, there are many considerations to choose the correct parts for the design. The considerations of choosing the appropriate antenna are:

1. Impedance of the antenna
2. Gain of the antenna

Taking the above design spec in consideration, the team found Yagi antennas that fit our spec. Below is a picture of the Yagi antenna.

Figure 5: A picture of the 9 dBi gain Yagi antenna

The impedance of the antenna should match with the output impedance of the power transmitter and input impedance of the rectifier circuit. Non-matching impedance between circuits can cause a tremendous power loss due to signal distortion. Since the output impedance of the transmitter is 50Ω , the antenna should also have 50Ω impedance.

The higher of the antenna gain yields a better result of the design. However, higher gain will also increase the cost and the size of the antenna. This becomes a major factor in choosing the antenna due to the group's limited financial resources. After consideration, a 9 dBi Yagi antenna is chosen for the design

3.3. Receiver

The receiver's main purpose is to charge an AAA battery. A simple battery charging theory is to run current through the battery, and apply a voltage difference between the terminals of the battery to reverse the chemical process. By doing so, it recharges the battery. There are other efficient and faster ways to charge the battery, but it requires a large amount of energy which the wireless battery charger cannot obtain, yet. Therefore, in our design, we use a straight forward method to charge the battery.

Microwave signal is an AC signal with a frequency range of 1 GHz – 1000 GHz. 900 MHz is in between the RF/ Microwave range. No matter how high the frequency is, AC signal is still AC signal. Therefore, the signal can also be treated as a low frequency AC signal. In order to get a DC signal out of the AC signal, a rectifier circuit is needed.

Figure 6: Full-wave Rectifier Circuit

A full-wave rectifier is chosen for the project due to its simplicity and efficiency in converting the AC signal. The full-wave rectifier is consisted of four diodes. Since the power received by the receiver will be relatively low and the signal frequency is high, the diodes are required to have a very low turn on voltage and operating frequency at 900 MHz. For this reason, a Schottky diode by Skyworks is chosen for the design.

At the output of the rectifier, the signal is not a fully DC signal yet. Thus, by adding a capacitor and a resistor can smooth out the output to become DC signal. However, the time constant produced by the capacitor and the resistor should be calculated carefully to fit the desired time constant.

Figure 7: Full-Wave Rectifier with Capacitor and resistor.

Receiver Design

The basic addition to the mobile phone is going to be type of antenna that is used to directly convert microwave energy into DC electricity. Actually the size of rectenna can be reduced using the Nano technology.

Fig 8: Whole set up for charging

We also have to add a sensor at receiver side. As we know we are going to charge the phone while a person is talking. So here sensor is used to detect whether the phone is using microwaves or not.

3.4. The Process of Rectification

Microwave can easily travel through the media but it also loses some energy. So our key objective is to rectify the circuit and to rectify the waves at the low cost. And also we have to make the detection more sensitive. As we know that bridge rectification is more efficient than the single diode we use this for the better performance. We use the Schottky diode to get the better impedance. The Schottky barrier diode is an ideal diode, such as for a 1 ampere limited current PN interface. Another advantage of the Schottky barrier diode is a very low noise index that is very important for a communication receiver; its working scope may reach 20GHz.

3.5. Sensor Circuitry

The sensor circuitry is a any message signal. This is very important as the phone has to be charged as long as the user is talking. . Thus a simple frequency to voltage converter would serve our purpose. And this converter would act as switches to trigger the rectenna circuit to on. Here in India the operating frequency of the GSM is 900 MHz to 1800 MHz. We can use LM2907 for F to V conversion. The general block diagram for the LM2907 is given below in fig.

Fig 9: Block diagram of LM2907

Thus on the reception of the signal the sensor circuitry directs the rectenna circuit to ON and the mobile phone begins to charge using the microwave power.

VI. TESTING AND DATA

After building the complete final designed circuit, we needed to know the output effectiveness in respect to distance. The following data was taken by using a multi-meter measuring voltage and current values versus the distance between the two antennas. Distance (ft)	Volts (V)	Current (mA)	Power (mW)
0.5	3.4	27	91.8
1	3.24	17.2	55.728
1.5	3.1	9.8	30.38
2	3	7.3	21.9
2.5	2.7	4	10.8
3	1.93	1.5	2.895
3.5	1.4	0.51	0.714
4	1.29	0.03	0.0387

Volts Vs. Distance 00.511.522.533.5400.511.522.533.544.5 **Distance (ft)** **Voltage (V)** Volts (V)

Figure 14a: Voltage versus distance chart

Current Vs Distance 05101520253000.511.522.533.544.5 **Distance (ft)** **Current (mA)** Current (mA)

Figure 14b: Current Vs. Distance Chart

ADVANTAGES

1. Charging of mobile phone is done wirelessly.
2. We can saving time for chageing mobiles.
3. Wastage of power is less.
4. Better than witrlicity as the distance the witrlicity can cover is about 20 meters whereas in this technology we are using base station for transmission that can cover more area.
5. Mobile get charged as we make call even during long journey.

DISADVANTAGES

1. Radiation problems may occur.
2. Network traffic may cause problem in charging.
3. Charging depends on network coverage.
4. Rate of charging may be minute range.

Marketing Plan

The working prototype uses Yagi antennas for the design. The prototype may not seem like an attractive design for today's wireless devices; however it could be implemented into other applications. For instance, it could be implemented onto devices in the tower and only charge up when needed. The team strives to improve the wireless charger using the spiral patch antennas in the future. The spiral antenna is able to pick up a wider range of frequencies instead of just tuned to one particular frequency. In addition, the spiral antennas become smaller at higher frequency which is small enough to fit in a cell phone or any wireless devices. The multiple rectifier design will also increase the received power. Therefore, these improvements show that this project still holds valid market demands.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, power loss and efficiency are the major problems for this design project. Our design team has noticed the potential problem whether the converted DC power will be significant enough to charge up the battery. Therefore, the characteristics of the diodes should be mounted directly onto the antenna for minimum power dissipation. In addition to harmonics, the nonlinear diode creates a DC-bias in the resonant circuit which can be extracted without affecting the RF/ microwave characteristics of the resonant circuit. The time varying voltage and current relationship at the physical point of the diode in the cavity determines the loss in the diode and, consequently, the RF/ microwave to DC efficiency.

As the wireless technology is getting popular nowadays, the demand of battery is also increasing. The battery needs to be recharged or changed eventually. Therefore our team is inspired to design the wireless battery charger. This wireless battery charger will eliminate all the hassle with the battery. As for now, there are no known companies which develop the wireless battery charger. This means that the opportunity is very big. Also, people tend to spend more money for convenience. It gives more reason that this device will have a very good market.

References

1. Kamal Acharya. School management system project report. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.34023165/v1>
2. Kamal Acharya. A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.30191075/v1>
3. Kamal Acharya. A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254872.26972790/v1>
4. Kamal Acharya. Web chatting application project report management system. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.18588592/v1>
5. Kamal Acharya. RETAIL STORE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.14590154/v1>
6. Kamal Acharya. SUPERMARKET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.19145062/v1>
7. Kamal Acharya. SOCIAL MEDIA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.11210579/v1>
8. Kamal Acharya. Online music portal management system project report. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252488.89734698/v1>
9. Kamal Acharya. COLLEGE BUS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245277.70798942/v1>
10. Kamal Acharya. AUTOMOBILE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245276.67982593/v1>
11. Kamal Acharya. Ludo management system project report. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243999.98091616/v1>
12. Kamal Acharya. Literature online quiz system project report. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243825.53562953/v1>
13. Kamal Acharya. Avoid waste management system project. Authorea. July 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228528.85022205/v1>
14. Kamal Acharya. CHAT APPLICATION THROUGH CLIENT SERVER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. July 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228527.74316529/v1>
15. Acharya, Kamal, Online Job Portal Management System (May 5, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
16. Acharya, Kamal, Employee leave management system. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>
17. Acharya, Kamal, Online electricity billing project report. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>
18. Acharya, Kamal, POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>
19. Acharya, Kamal, Online job placement system project report. (January 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831638> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831638>
20. Acharya, Kamal, Software testing for project report. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>
21. Acharya, Kamal, ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>
22. Acharya, Kamal, Burger ordering system project report. (October 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>
23. Acharya, Kamal, Teachers Record Management System Project Report (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4833821> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4833821>
24. Acharya, Kamal, Dairy Management System Project Report (December 20, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835231> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835231>

25. Acharya, Kamal, *Electrical Shop Management System Project* (December 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835238> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835238>
26. Acharya, Kamal, *Online book store management system project report*. (February 10, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835277> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835277>
27. Acharya, Kamal, *Paint shop management system project report*. (January 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835441> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835441>
28. Acharya, Kamal, *Supermarket billing system project report*. (August 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835474> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835474>
29. Acharya, Kamal, *Online taxi booking system project report*. (March 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837729> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837729>
30. Acharya, Kamal, *Online car servicing system project report*. (March 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837832> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837832>
31. Acharya, Kamal, *School management system project report*. (July 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837837> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837837>
32. Acharya, Kamal, *Furniture Showroom Management System Project Report* (March 21, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839422> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839422>
33. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Vehicle Rental System Project Report* (March 21, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839429> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839429>
34. Acharya, Kamal, *Fruit Shop Management System Project Report* (August 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841048> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841048>
35. Acharya, Kamal, *Hall Booking Management System Project Report* (December 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841055> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841055>
36. Acharya, Kamal, *Lundry Management System Project Report* (October 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841059> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841059>
37. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT* (September 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841209> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841209>
38. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT* (May 25, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841210> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841210>
39. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE DATING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842066> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842066>
40. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE RESUME BUILDER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842071> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842071>
41. Acharya, Kamal, *TOLL TEX MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT* (August 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842082> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842082>
42. Acharya, Kamal, *Chat Application Through Client Server Management System Project Report* (June 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842761> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842761>
43. Acharya, Kamal, *Web Chatting Application Management System Project Report* (April 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842771> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842771>
44. Acharya, Kamal, *Automobile management system project report* (May 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846917> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846917>
45. Acharya, Kamal, *College bus management system project report* (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846920> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846920>
46. Acharya, Kamal, *Courier management system project report* (May 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846922> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846922>

47. Acharya, Kamal, *Event management system project report* (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846927> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846927>
48. Acharya, Kamal, *Library management system project report II* (May 25, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4848857> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4848857>